

**Professional ethics of a lawyer and its social significance
in the Republic of Uzbekistan**

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ABSTRACT:

Modern advocacy plays a significant role in the system of government as it establishes and sustains specific connections between lawyers and ordinary people. The text highlights the pivotal role of lawyers in protecting human rights and interests, stressing the need for high standards of professionalism and ethics. It discusses the importance of legal ethics in ensuring fairness, legality, and morality in professional conduct, regulated by laws and codes of conduct. Additionally, it emphasizes the moral responsibility of lawyers to maintain integrity and dignity, even in challenging situations, to uphold public trust in the legal profession. Overall, it underscores the critical significance of ethical behavior in legal practice for preserving the profession's integrity and societal trust.

Keywords: Lawyer, law, social, professional, behavior, Decree, legal, rules, human, ethics, principles, the Chamber of Advocates, freedom, honor, rights, dignity, protection, competence, client, self-justification, independence, standards, skills, duties, reforms, society, culture, the Code, grievance.

"I'd like to serve, but not to be a servant!"

A.S. Griboyedov, "Woe from Wi.

The profession of a lawyer is directly related to the protection of human interests, such as rights, freedoms, honor and dignity, and to a large extent determines the fate of a person. For this reason, the legal profession, along with other professions such as doctors, teachers, judges, prosecutors and others, which also aim to assist and protect human beings (including their life, health, education, and rights and freedoms), are held to their own high standards of professionalism, ethics and fairness. These principles underpin their legal defense and legal aid activities.

The purpose of professional ethics, as in any field, including the legal profession, is to ensure that high standards of behavior, principles of fairness, legality and morality are observed in professional activities [1].

In accordance with the requirements set out in the Laws "On the Advocacy" and "On Guarantees of Advocacy and Social Protection of Advocates", lawyers of the Republic of Uzbekistan have certain rights and duties, and enjoy the protection of laws that ensure the independence and inviolability of their professional activities. In addition to these Laws, a Presidential Decree was signed on 12 May 2018, aimed at radically improving the effectiveness of the institution of the Bar and expanding the independence of lawyers [2]. The Decree notes the significant work carried out in recent years in the country aimed at enhancing the role and significance of the Bar as one of the key instruments for the protection of the rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of individuals and legal entities in the context of judicial and legal reforms[3].

The Institute of Advocacy, being aware of its moral responsibility to society, carries out its activities on the basis of the Rules of Professional Ethics of Advocates, which was promulgated on 27.09.2013 by the II Conference of the Chamber of Advocates of the Republic of Uzbekistan [4]. Thus, legal ethics is a scientific direction that analyses the requirements for moral and ethical qualities necessary for employees of the legal sphere, in addition, studies the features of the culture of legal activity. The professional activities of a judge, prosecutor, investigator are characterized by their peculiarities and direct impact on the rights and interests of people, which highlights the importance of identifying and assessing the moral content of their work [5]. In addition, the duties and rights of lawyers are also regulated in other legislation, including the Code of Criminal Procedure, the Code of Civil Procedure, the Code of Economic Procedure and other similar documents.

This set of Rules includes the principles of honesty, confidentiality, dedication to the client's interests, competence, as well as compliance with laws and professional standards. Such rules define the immutable rules of behavior and relations with both clients and colleagues, as well as establish requirements for the quality of services provided by lawyers. Moreover, a lawyer must maintain an appropriate demeanor and dress code that meets all the requirements of business standards. Continuous improvement of his/her knowledge and professional skills is also an important part of his/her duties. Compliance with these Rules helps to maintain public confidence in the legal profession and ensure effective protection of the rights and interests of clients.

Another important principle is the observance of the advocate's secrecy, which is understood as "all information related to the provision of legal assistance by an advocate to his/her client". The law prohibits an advocate from disclosing information provided by a client in connection with the provision of legal assistance

without the client's consent. A lawyer is bound by ethical and legal principles of confidentiality: he/she cannot be called and questioned as a witness regarding information obtained by him/her in the course of providing legal assistance or as a consequence thereof [6].

Ethical principles become a reliable guide for lawyers in making decisions in a variety of situations, including specific issues, problems, and behavioral strategies for both themselves and their clients. These principles are particularly important because it is impossible to anticipate all possible cases in advance. Nevertheless, in every situation, a lawyer should justify his/her actions to himself/herself, clients, the state, society, colleagues and his/her profession, demonstrating a high level of professionalism and ethics.

The introductory statement placed at the beginning of this research paper is a famous phrase of A.S. Griboyedov from the work "Woe from Wit". This quote has been carefully chosen to establish relevance to the research topic. In a number of cases, a lawyer's behavior towards his client should always be of a high standard, regardless of the surrounding circumstances [7]. Even if the client unfairly accuses the lawyer of incompetence or lack of commitment to the case, the lawyer must remain discreet and respectful, explaining his or her point of view to the client and explaining in detail the reasons for his or her actions or inactions that caused the grievance. At the same time, it is important that the lawyer's explanations do not sound like excuses or contain elements of self-justification, especially when the lawyer is sure of the correctness of his actions.

According to generally accepted rules, advocates are subject to disciplinary measures, such as reprimands or warnings, for breaches of professional standards. In case of a serious or systematic violation of the legislation or ethical norms governing the practice of law, an advocate's license may be revoked [8]. In deciding whether to impose disciplinary measures, the Chamber of Advocates may take into account a variety of factors, including the absence of previous offences, the existence of rewards, admissions of guilt and attempts to remedy the situation [9]. At the same time, factors such as health status, the presence of minor dependent children, financial obligations or specialization in a particular area of law are not taken into account when deciding whether to hold an advocate liable [10].

In conclusion, it should be stressed that advocates must always preserve the honor and dignity inherent in their profession, regardless of the circumstances. The obligation to comply with the rules of advocate's ethics arises from the attribution of advocate's status. If issues of advocate's professional ethics are not regulated by

legislation, an advocate must follow the customs and traditions established in the legal profession that correspond to generally accepted moral principles in society.

References:

1. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan «On the Advocacy» from 27.12.1996. №349-I.
2. Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan «On guarantees of advocates' practice and social protection of advocates» dated December 25, 1998 No.721-I.
3. Appendix No. 8 to the decision of the II Conference of the Chamber of Advocates of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Rules of professional ethics of advocates dated 27.09.2013.
4. Constitutional bases of the advocate's activity.
https://constitution.uz/ru/pages/advokatskaya_deyatelnost.
5. V.D Sheshenya., N.V. Kulazhenkova. On the professional ethics of a lawyer. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/k-voprosu-o-professionalnoy-etike-advokata>.
6. Y.D. Kokambo, O.V. Skorobogatova. Legal nature and limits of the code of professional ethics of a lawyer. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/pravovaya-priroda-i-predely-deystviya-kodeksa-professionalnoy-etiki-advokata>
7. S.V. Kartavtseva, O.V. Skorobogatova. Legal bases of the professional activity of an advocate. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/pravovye-osnovy-professionalnoy-deyatelnosti-advokata>.
8. D.O. Nechiporuk Moscow University for the Humanitie. Moral foundations of the lawyer's activity. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/nravstvennye-osnovy-deyatelnosti-advokata>.
9. Бурханова Л. М. ОСОБЕННОСТИ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ КУРСА «ГРАЖДАНСКОЕ ПРАВО» С ПРИМЕНЕНИЕМ ИНТЕРАКТИВНЫХ И ИННОВАЦИОННЫХ МЕТОДИК: ВОПРОСЫ ТЕОРИИ И ПРАКТИКИ ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ //Oriental renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences. – 2023. – Т. 3. – №. 3. – С. 1195-1207.
10. Бурханова Л. М. ОСОБЕННОСТИ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЯ ЦИФРОВЫХ ТЕХНОЛОГИЙ В ПРОЦЕССЕ ПРЕПОДАВАНИЯ В ТАШКЕНТСКОМ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННОМ ЮРИДИЧЕСКОМ УНИВЕРСИТЕТЕ //ББК 94.31 П78. – 2023. – С. 119.